

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF WASTE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM USING IOT

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Abstract — Waste management is a major issue in many areas and the current waste management system is not enough to handle the increasing amount of waste generated daily. Our idea is based on the concept of IOT (internet of things) used in waste management system. This system provides an efficient way of managing waste and lead to good environmental impact. This system employs sensors like infrared, ultrasonic and load to gather the data based on types wastes and level of trash bin for further process. Most importantly it employs microprocessor (Raspberry Pi) to sort the waste in respected trash bin with the help of robot arms. This microprocessor is also responsible for sending the notification through mobile application which reaches the workers. Main concept of our system is to segregate the waste based on recyclable percentage . The efficiency, sustainability, and reliability of waste management techniques might all be greatly increased by using an IOT-based trash management system..

KEYWORDS – IOT, Microprocessor, waste, sensor, robot-arms, mobile-application, recyclable-waste , trash bin.

I. INTRODUCTION

The amount of waste generated daily by households, businesses, and the general public is rising at the fastest rate

possible, and incorrect waste disposal is a major contributing factor to this issue. Many innovative and diverse methods are employed in developed nations to properly manage waste, but in certain developing nations, particularly, people's negligence towards preserving a clean environment and population growth is the root cause of waste management's deadly consequences. The trash cans in our culture serve as breeding grounds for bacteria, insects, and flies—the same flies that swarm around edibles and release their young. As a result, they raise the risk of food poisoning, typhoid, dengue fever, malaria, and other illnesses. The 377 million people who live in metropolitan India produce 62 million tonnes of waste every day, making India the third-largest garbage generator in the world, according to the International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology. But what's more concerning is not how much waste is produced, but rather the fact that every day, municipal authorities dispose of about 45 million tons—roughly equivalent to three million trucks—of untreated, unsanitary garbage. (Vol. 9 Issue 04, April-2020). So The IOT is an concept to the collective network of connected devices and technology can be used to create an intelligent waste management system that will help manage the waste efficiently . Our project is about the way we organize the waste disposal using robots that pick up the waste using sensor detection and segregates the waste . its not like other segregating trash bin because it segregate the waste based on the recyclable percentage.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Waste Collection System with Infrared Sensors and Internet of Things [1] Using artificial neural networks, a modern classification method, this automatic debris segregator divides the waste into multiple groups. This technology enables improved recycling and reuse practices that support waste management. The project's objective is to develop and construct an effective garbage separation system by employing the concepts of artificial neural networks and image analysis, particularly the image recognition method. .

The project's aim is to design and build a system of trash segregation that can be utilised to efficiently separate waste utilising artificial neural networks [2]. Artificial Neural Networks can be employed to classify waste types according to the suggested manner by applying recognition and classification techniques.

Referencing [3], an electronic monitoring system with GSM was developed so that when the trashcan is full, the supervisor receives an SMS and a truck for waste collection is sent. An SMS alerting the supervisor to waste collection is sent to them once more. In order to determine how much rubbish was in the trash can, the author of that study used an ultrasonic sensor. A GSM module was then used to transmit a message to the recipient letting them know if the dustbin had been filled or cleaned.

Similar methods for gathering trash utilising an Arduino UNO board interfaced with a GSM module and an ultrasonic sensor were described in [4]. The study's author discussed issues with smart dustbin pricing, upkeep, and durability. A waste management system that collects trash from hard-to-reach places in the city utilising a camera, an Arduino UNO, and a Wi-Fi module module that connects to the internet through the Blynk app, which manages all of the participant communication [5].

The authors of [6] provide a system dubbed cloud-based smart waste management (Cloud SWAM). It provides a solution that consists of specialised bins for all waste types (plastic, metal, organic, and bottle) that are equipped with sensors to monitor and update their state in real time to the cloud, where interested parties can connect and get relevant data.

An Internet of Things-based sensor system is used to gauge the amount of waste. These smart bins' location is determined by the GPS system. Through GSM on smartphones, the location data is sent to the waste management department. [7] One can locate the dustbin's position by using Google Maps.

In [8], the authors provide a method that uses intelligent monitoring to enable garbage collection scheduling. The Smart-M3 platform (extension of cross-domain search for triple-based information) facilitates cooperative application development and implementation across a wide range of information and communication domains.

III. EXISTING SYSTEM

The waste management system with recycling of waste using IOT is exist in manner. This management system has bin robots with network of sensors, connected devices and robots to collect the waste then segregate the waste by recycling waste and non-recycling waste.

The first step in the process is the establishing the sensors and connected devices throughout the waste and recycling system and then the sensor would monitor the types of waste being generated and whether it is applicable to recyclable or not.

The data is collected from the sensor is being analyzed using machine learning algorithms and the robot is collect the waste, sort the waste materials like the robot is recognize the different types of plastics, metals and glass products to sort them into separate trash bins.

Once the waste has be sorted and that are sent to the recycling facility for reusability, so that the recycling process could be computerized using robots and IOT devices, further improving efficiency and manage waste

IV. PROPOSING SYSTEM

As we know that developed waste management system can separate waste as recyclable and non-recyclable. This system can ensure the waste segregation based on the recyclable percentage such as degradable, (60 - 79%) recyclable, (80 - 100%) recyclable, non-recyclable waste.

This system can use image Recognition technique to identify type of waste by using camera module and

CNN model then with the help of robot arms attached it can pick and drop the waste to respective dustbins.

Once the bin filled or reaches the certain threshold value it can be monitored by microprocessor then notification can sent to worker via mobile application to make the bin empty.

This system is an Internet of Things based intelligent

waste management system (IOT). This system will help to reduce waste ,improve waste management efficiency , and help to protect the environment.

IV.A PROPOSING SYSTEM’S ADVANTAGE

As this system segregating the waste based on recyclable percentage it is easy to treat the waste for reuse purpose.

For example the existing system segregate the waste has recyclable and non-recyclable so compare to this proposing system the existing systems is not that must effective because if we are segregating the waste based on 60-79% and 80-100% .The waste with recyclable percentage of 51-80% could be recycle in a fast manner and can be reuse .

if we recycle all the waste which has different recyclable percent levels , together it takes more time to process It (consider the waste cloth bags and recyclable plastic).

Thus our project helps to recycle it easily based on the recyclable percent level thus optimizing the time.

IV.B METHEDODOLOGY

Robot has an IOT (internet of things) interface with autonomous mode of control .The trash in the trash bin is picked up using robotic arm.The picked up trash is segregated as biodegradable waste ,60 - 79% recyclable waste (non – biodegradable) 80 - 100% recyclable waste (non-bio degradable) and other non - biodegradable waste dumped into bin which is attached to the robot arm that has four partitions .

In autonomous mode the robot pick up the waste that are done without humans intervention.The robot is placed at the center of the workspace . Firstly the image recognition technique the detect the waste and microprocessor instruct the robot to pick and segregate the waste . The robot arms can turn in 360 degree . Based on this way our system is used to segregated the waste . Once the trash bin are filled the information will send to municipality workers through mobile application which the help of sensors.

I. PROCESS FLOWCHART

II. ARCHITECTURE

III. COMPONENTS

1.Trash bin: Typical Dustbin Composed of metal , it has a space for the sensors to be placed and can hold garbage. There are four bins in total in this system: one for non-recyclable waste, one for recyclable waste (80–100%), one for recyclable waste (60–79%) , and one for degradable waste.

2.Sensors : A variety of sensors are included in this waste management system to identify the kind, quantity , and weight of the waste . After the data is gathered , it is transferred to the " Raspberry Pi " microprocessor for additional processing. We are utilising load measurement and ultrasonic sensor kinds in this system.

1. ULTRASONIC SENSOR

To find out how much waste is there, it can be mounted on top of the trash can.once it emits the sound wave, it travels down to the surface and bounces back to the sensor . Then it calculates the distance between itself and the time it took for the sound wave to travel back and forth. By measuring time it can determine the level of bin.

2. LOAD SENSOR

It is installed beneath the trash can, and a sensor detects the weight as rubbish is added. It is used to track the amount of rubbish in the bin and can give more accurate information.

IV. IMAGE RECOGNIZATION

- ❖ Once the waste is disposed to our common bin the camera module attached at the of Bin can starts to capture the image.
- ❖ After capturing it can perform Pre-Processing i.e.
- ❖ Image Resizing to reduce the complexity.
- ❖ Once the architecture has been established , you can train the CNN's using the training set.Update the mode's weights and biases using backpropagation in order to reduce the loss function.
- ❖ Examine how well the CNN model performs on the testing set once it has been trained. Metrics

including accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score can be used to evaluate the model's performance.

- ❖ The CNN model can be implemented in your waste management system once it has been trained and evaluated . The model can be used to automate the garbage sorting process and classify waste photos in real-time.
- ❖ Once the architecture has been established, you can train the using the training set. Update the model's weights and biases using backpropagation in order to reduce the loss function . Evaluate the CNN model's performance on the testing set after it has been trained. Make use of metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score to evaluate the model's performance.
- ❖ The CNN model can be implemented in your waste management system once it has been trained and evaluated.

The model can be used to automate the garbage sorting process and classify waste photos in real-time It can instruct the robot arm to pick and drop the waste in respected trash bin.

V. RASPBERRY PI

It is the important component which plays many roles in this system

Figure 1 : Diagram of Raspberry pi

1.Sensor Integration:

Raspberry Pi can be used to integrate different types of sensors such as ultrasonic sensors, weight sensors, and infrared sensors to monitor the waste bin fill level, temperature, and other parameters.

2 . Data Collection and Analysis:

The Raspberry Pi can collect the data from the sensors and analyze to determine optimized waste collection and use the robot arms to sort waste based on its types.

3.Real Time Monitoring :

The Raspberry Pi can be used to link to the internet and provide real-time sensor data to a cloud-based platform for real-time monitoring. After that, the load sensor and ultrasonic sensor's updated values are communicated to a specially created mobile application for the workers.

4.Robot arms:

This system can include two robot arms attached at the both sides of the dustbin. with the help of raspberry pi it will be instructed to pick and drop the waste in respective dustbin. There can be four joints for the both arms each would be able to move in specific angles.

Figure 2: Diagram of bin’s arm (Robot arms)

- ❖ The robot arm's motors can be managed with a motor controller.
- ❖ The Raspberry Pi can be used to control the robot arm by connecting the motor controller to it.
- ❖ The motor controller is pololu maestro.
- ❖ These controller are used to controll the servo motor which is in robot arm and they can be controlled by USB interface.
- ❖ This has variety of features such as speed, position and acceleration control as well as scripting capabilities also.

5.Mobile Application :

In this system, the mobile application provides a solution to manage the waste efficiently . When bins are full and needs to emptied means the notification will be sent to mobile application with the help of internet connection, this is controlled by the Raspberry Pi.

GSM(MOBILE COMMUNICATION):

In this system, the mobile application provides a solution to manage the waste efficiently . When bins are full and needs to emptied means the notification will be sent to mobile application with the help of internet connection, this is controlled by the Raspberry Pi.

Messages sending and receiving can be controlled by GSM-Global System for Mobile application. Here GSM modem or GSM module can be connected to Raspberry pi through USB.

Gammu Library is one of the most popular library which can be installed on raspberry pi to enable communication with GSM module. Instead of sending text messages the custom alert system can send notification to mobile application whenever the trash bin become full or reached certain threshold value.

VI. WASTE SEGREGATION AND MANAGEMENT

After image recognition, the Raspberry Pi receives the information and directs the robot arms to collect the rubbish and place it in the appropriate trash can.After that, it can have additional sensors, such as load and ultrasonic, to keep the waste in the trash can.

Once the ultrasonic sensor which is mounted on the top of the each bins will creates the sound wave that travels lowest part of bin and then bounces back to this sensor, by measuring the amount of time it requires to travel back and forth it will determine the level of bin.

Then we can also measure the weight with the help of load sensor which is mounted under each bin, when the waste is added weight is also increased and by this way it evaluated the threshold weight. Once it reaches the certain threshold value or certain level of the bin it needs to be emptied .

VII. MODEL

Figure 3: of our model(Four bin’s with robotic arm attac

VIII. SAMPLE

Sample	Materials of samples	Recyclable percentage	Belongs to which type of bin	Pictures
1	High density polyethylene and low density polyethylene, polyester	85%	80-100% (bin)	
2	Transparent water bottle	30%	Non-degradable bin	
3	Clothes	69%	60-79%(bin)	

Figure 4 : Diagram of classification tabular(Example)

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V. RESULT:

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OVERVIEW OF OUR SYSTEM

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Figure 5 : Pictorial representation of our model

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VI. CONCLUSION

Waste that is not properly maintained and disposed of can have negative consequences on the environment and public health. This proposed system can address these issues by properly segregating waste according to recycling percentage. All things considered, this approach may greatly increase the efficacy, sustainability, and efficiency of waste management techniques.

VII. FUTURE WORKS

In future this system can be developed by bringing the way to decompose the bio degradable waste without human intervention with proper management that optimize the time and decomposing the medical waste in efficient manner.

VIII. REFERENCE

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